

Root resorption risk modeling

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Abstract

We proposed to study nine clinical and treatment-related factors and polymorphisms of four genes in order to construct a model to predict orthodontic-induced external apical root resorption (EARR). We concluded that the main factors contributing to the EARR process are gender, treatment duration, use of a Hyrax appliance, premolar extractions and rs1718119 polymorphism of the P2RX7 gene. These five variables explained 27% of EARR variability, suggesting the existence of other aetiologic factors. This study has been recently published in the journal *Oral Diseases* (Pereira et al, 2013).

Keywords: Apical Root Resorption, Gene Polymorphism, Orthodontics, P2RX7 Gene

1. Introduction

External apical root resorption (EARR) is a frequent complication observed in association with orthodontic tooth movement and has been of great concern to clinical researchers. Although forces applied and tooth movement are the trigger for EARR, studies have shown that biomechanical factors may not account for more than one-tenth to one-third of the variation observed in root resorption. Many factors have been described including medication, endodontic treatment and patients' intrinsic factors such as gender, age, tongue thrust, the existence of anterior open bite, type of malocclusion and systemic diseases.

In this study we also included four genes, extensively explored as susceptible markers, as candidates for root resorption modeling. The polymorphisms chosen for this study have previously been associated with EARR or bone remodeling and might be functionally relevant: rs1143634 from IL-1B, rs3102735 from OPG gene, rs1805034 from RANK gene and rs1718119 from P2RX7.

1.1. Materials and Methods

For this retrospective study, patients followed by the same orthodontist were randomly selected from the archives of two orthodontic clinics and from the Department of Orthodontics,

Dentistry, Faculty of Medicine of Coimbra. The 195 selected patients included 72 males and 123 females, with an average age of 17.24 years (s.d. 6.8 years).

Before and after orthodontic treatment panoramic radiographs were used to evaluate the percentage of EARR for each patient based on measurements on six teeth, the four maxillary incisors (ISO System codes 11, 12, 21 and 22) and the two maxillary canines (ISO System codes 13 and 23). Measurements were conducted using a software prototype developed by the authors using Matlab, that included image preprocessing, point selection (manually marking 4 points on each selected tooth) and feature extraction to produce a set of linear measurements for parts (crown and root) of the teeth under analysis. The corrected final root measurement results from the application of a correction or enlargement factor corresponding to the ratio between the initial and final crown lengths, because it is accepted that during orthodontic treatment, the crown length does not change. In order to analyse the EARR phenomena for the individual and not only for each separate tooth, we propose a metric based on the maximum observed EARR (EARRmax) on the six selected teeth.

Eighteen explanatory variables were included in a stepwise regression (mixed forward/backward option) having EARRmax as dependent variable and the following explanatory variables: gender (binary), age (years), treatment duration (months), anterior open bite (binary), premolar extractions (binary), Hyrax appliance (binary), tongue thrust (binary), overjet (continuous orthodontic measure), skeletal class (3 categories, thus 2 binary variables), polymorphisms from TNFRSF11A, TNFRSF11B, IL-1B and P2RX7 genes (3 categories for each, thus 8 binary variables).

Table 1. External apical root resorption (%) statistics for each tooth (n=195).

Statistics	Tooth						
	13	12	11	21	22	23	
Average	8.0	11.5	9.5	9.9	10.2	8.3	
Standard deviation	6.9	8.6	8.2	9.6	8.1	7.2	
Maximum	47.7	37.0	42.1	49.7	37.0	35.4	
Percentile	25	2.8	4.8	3.5	2.7	3.5	2.9
	50	6.2	9.5	7.2	6.3	8.2	6.6
	75	11.1	17.5	13.9	13.8	15.0	11.3
	95	22.4	29.0	26.4	31.6	26.6	23.7

2. Results

Characterization of the teeth's EARR is depicted in Table 1. On average, EARR ranged from 8% (tooth 13) to 11.5% (tooth 12). The difference between canines' and incisors' EARR average was significant, while there were no significant differences within incisors or between symmetrical teeth (repeated-measures ANOVA: Wilks' lambda = 0.826, F = 7.998, P < 0.0005; post hoc tests: P < 0.0005 only for differences between canines' and incisors' EARR average). The EARR median ranged from 6.2% (tooth 13) to 9.5% (tooth 12). According to the value of percentile 95, five percent of patients showed EARR higher than 22.4% on tooth 13 and higher than 31.6% on tooth 21.

The stepwise model at the final stage showed that the selected variables explained 27% of the EARRmax variability (ANOVA: F = 15.315, P = 0.000; adjusted determination coefficient = 0.270, n = 195) and that the selected variables were (Table 2): gender (P < 0.05), treatment duration (P < 0.001), premolar extractions (P < 0.01), Hyrax appliance (P < 0.001) and GG genotype for the P2RX7 gene (P < 0.01).

Table 2 - Results of stepwise regression model

Parameters of statistical model	N (%)	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		P value
		B	SD	Beta	t	
(Constant)		7.6	2.4		3.145	.002
Female	123 (63%)	-3.2	1.2	-0.162	-2.580	.011
Duration of treatment (months)		0.3	0.1	0.275	4.270	.000
Pre-molar extraction	58 (30%)	4.0	1.3	0.193	2.990	.003
Hyrax appliance	14 (7%)	8.4	2.3	0.230	3.599	.000
P2RX7, GG genotype (baseline AA genotype)	84 (43%)	3.1	1.2	0.162	2.595	.010

The generalizability of our findings is supported by a 75/25% cross-validation. We verified that the model based on a training sample (n = 159) included the same five variables as the model based on the full data set (n=195) and also that the stepwise algorithm reaches convergence also after five iterations. Finally, we compared the accuracy of the model for the validation sample (n = 36) to the accuracy of the model for the training sample, resulting in a value of .0033 for shrinkage. Thus the validation was successful.

Table 2 also describes the contributions of factors included in the multiple linear regression model, assuming that all other variables remain constant: on average, female values on EARR were 3.2% below male values; each additional month of treatment represented an average increase of 0.3% ; patients with premolar extractions had about 4% higher values than

those without; use of Hyrax appliance increased the amount of EARRmax by 8%; the presence of GG genotype on the P2RX7 gene was associated with an average increase of 3%.

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References

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